

Alkylation of β -Ketosulphoxides with Electrophilic Olefins

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β -ketosulphoxides undergo facile Michael reaction with α , β -unsaturated esters, ketones and nitriles. Reductive cleavage of the C-S bond, in the Michael reaction products so obtained, with aluminium amalgam in aq. T.H.F. provides a series of attractive multifunctional organic compounds.

In the course of our synthetic investigations in terpenoids employing β -ketosulphoxides as key intermediates¹, we were fascinated to explore some of their interesting reactions which may further widen their scope as valuable synthetic reagents. In fact the easy availability of β -ketosulphoxides, by the action of methyl sulphanyl carbanion on ester² or by the condensation of dimethyl sulphoxide with ester in the presence of a strong base³, and their increasing importance as synthetic intermediates in organic chemistry, prompted us to examine their chemical properties in detail. Russel and coworkers⁴ have already reported their versatile nature as synthetic intermediates by converting them into a variety of compounds. It was recently observed by Gassman *et al.*⁵ that β -ketosulphoxides form carbanions in solution when treated with sodium hydride in dimethyl formamide or dimethyl sulphoxide and these carbanions can undergo mono- or di-alkylations with primary halides. Alkylation of β -ketosulphoxides coupled with the facile reductive cleavage with aluminium amalgam has greatly enhanced the scope of Corey-Chaykovsky ketone synthesis². As a natural extension of this work, we studied the reaction of β -ketosulphoxide anion with α , β -unsaturated carbonyl systems and this forms the subject matter of the present communication.

Michael Reaction with α , β -unsaturated ketones : Methyl vinyl ketone when exposed to the carbanion (II) generated by the interaction of sodium ethoxide and β -ketosulphoxide (I) in dry D.M.F. underwent Michael reaction smoothly. The product after elimination

1. O. P. Vig, Romesh Anand and Baldev Vig (unpublished work).
2. E. J. Corey and M. J. Chayovsky, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 1639; 1965, **87**, 1345.
3. H. D. Becker, G. J. Mikol and G. A. Russel, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1896; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3410.
4. G. A. Russel and G. J. Mikol, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 5498.
5. P. G. Gassman and G. D. Richmond, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 2355.

of the methyl sulphanyl group with aluminium amalgam in aq. T.H.F. produced the diketone (III), in good yield as shown below :—

To prove the authenticity of the proposed structure (III) prepared by the sulphoxide route (vide supra), alternate synthesis of this compound was carried out as outlined below⁶ :—

The infra-red spectra of this compound (III) prepared by the above two routes were superimposable.

The present synthesis thus opens up an easily accessible route for the preparation of 2 : 6-dicarbonyl compounds as compared to the earlier method described by Stork⁷ and co-workers. The Michael reactions with other substituted alicyclic α , β -unsaturated ketones were also studied and the results are shown in the chart given below. It is of interest that under the present conditions employed 3-methyl-cyclohexenone reacted easily in contrast to its usual behaviour in Michael addition, firstly studied by Farmer and Ross⁸ and later on modified by Raphael *et al.*⁹ who have found the reaction to be quite slow and time taking.

CHART*

α , β -unsaturated carbonyl functions	Solvent used	Products obtained	% yield
Methyl-vinyl-ketone (1.0 mole)	D.M.F.	2 : 6-Diketo-8-methyl-nonane (III)	60
Mesityloxide (1.0 mole)	„	2 : 6-Diketo-4 : 4 : 8-trimethyl-nonane (IIIa)	50
3-Methyl-cyclohex-2-ene-1-one (1.0 mole)	„	3-Methyl-3(4-methyl-pentanone-2)-cyclohexanone (IIIb)	56
Ethyl-acrylate (1.0 mole)	„	1-Carbethoxy-6-methyl-heptan-4-one (VIII)	65
Ethyl- α -methyl-acrylate (1.0 mole)	„	1-Carbethoxy-1,6-dimethyl-heptan-4-one (VIIIa)	53
Ethyl-crotonate (1.0 mole)	„	1-Carbethoxy-2,6-dimethyl-heptan-4-one (VIIIb)	62
Acrylic nitrile (1.0 mole)	„	1-Cyano-6-methyl-heptan-4-one (IX)	70

* While this work was under print, a similar approach to β -keto-esters has been reported by G. A. Russel *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, **34**, 3624).

Reaction with α , β -unsaturated esters : Ethyl acrylate reacted with the carbanion (II) of the β -ketosulphoxide in D.M.F. readily and after reductive cleavage of the resulting product, formed the keto-ester (VIII) in good yield. No difficulty was encountered in the reaction of the carbanion with α - and β -substituted acrylic esters. Thus the δ -keto-esters were

7. G. Stork and R. Borch, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 935.

8. E. H. Farmer and J. Ross, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2358.

9. R. D. H. Murray, W. Parkar and R. A. Raphael, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, **16**, 74.

obtained in high yield as shown in the chart. The equation in general with ethyl acrylate can be represented as :—

The structures of δ -ketoesters have been confirmed by I.R. spectra and elemental analysis.

Reaction with Acrylic nitrile : Acrylic nitrile condenses with the carbanion (II) under the influence of sodium ethoxide in D.M.F. Removal of the methyl sulphanyl group provides the corresponding keto-nitrile (IX), thus involving a four carbon atom homologation.

EXPERIMENTAL*

1-Methyl sulphanyl-4-methyl-pentanone-2 (I) : Methyl sulphanyl carbanion was prepared in the usual manner under an atmosphere of nitrogen from NaH (4.8 g.) and dry dimethylsulphoxide (100 ml.). An equal volume of dry tetrahydrofuran was added and the solution was cooled in an ice bath. Isovaleric ester (13.0 g.) was added dropwise with stirring over a period of about 20 mins. The ice-bath was removed and the contents were stirred for an hour more at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured into sufficient amount of water, acidified with aqueous HCl and thoroughly extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed with brine and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish the β -ketosulphoxide (I) as a thick oil, b.p. 210–15°/3–5 mm., yield = 11.10 g. (69%). (Found : C, 52.03; H, 8.45. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{SO}_2$ requires : C, 51.85; H, 8.64%).

* B.ps. are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer infra-cord with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid film. The synthesised products were purified through chromatography over alumina using petroleum ether : benzene mixtures in varying proportions. D.M.F. used was dried over calcium hydride.

2 : 6-Diketo-8-methyl-nonane (III) : β -ketosulphoxide (I, 3.0 g.) in D.M.F. (10.0 ml.) was added to a stirred suspension of sodium ethoxide (1.3 g.) in D.M.F. (10.0 ml.). The mixture was stirred well for half an hour. To the anion (II) formed was added methyl vinyl ketone (1.4 g.) dropwise and with stirring. Considerable heat was produced during the alkylation reaction and the contents were left overnight at room temperature for the completion of the reaction. The reaction mixture was poured into sufficient amount of cold water and extracted with ether. The combined ether extracts were washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was evaporated to yield the alkylated β -ketosulphoxide (3.9 g.).

The above β -ketosulphoxide was dissolved in 10 per cent aqueous tetrahydrofuran (240 ml.) in a 500 ml. 3-necked flask equipped with a stirrer. Freshly prepared aluminium amalgam (from aluminium 5.0 g. and 2% mercuric chloride solution) was added in about 5 mins. to the stirred solution. The stirring was continued and the contents were heated in a water bath at 65° for a period of about 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was then filtered and the residue washed many times with T.H.F. The filtrate was concentrated to remove most of the T.H.F. and the residue was taken up in ether. The ether layer was separated from water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent evaporated. Distillation of the residue under pressure provided the diketone (III), b.p. 100–105°/7 mm; yield 1.88 g. (60%); η_D^{25} 1.5140. (Found : C, 70.75; H, 10.52. $C_{10}H_{18}O_2$ requires : C, 70.54; H, 10.66%).

I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1710 cm^{-1} , broad, (ketone), 1450 cm^{-1} and 1375 cm^{-1} (C–Me).

8-Methyl-4-carbethoxy-nonan-2,6-dione (V) : To a solution of the ketoester (IV, 10 g.), prepared exactly as described in literature¹⁰; in absolute ethanol (120 ml.) cooled to –10° was added sodium ethoxide (prepared from 60 mg. of sodium). This was followed by the dropwise addition of methyl vinyl ketone (4.4 g.) in about 40 mins. and the resulting mixture was kept at –10° for 3 hrs. Thereafter the base was neutralised with excess of acetic acid and the solvent removed under vacuum. The residue was extracted thoroughly with ether and the combined ether extract washed with $NaHCO_3$ solution and brine. Removal of the solvent and distillation afforded the diketoeester (V, 7.4 g.), b.p. 120–25°/2–3 mm., in 52.6% yield. (Found : C, 64.52; H, 9.21. $C_{13}H_{22}O_4$ requires : C, 64.44; H, 9.15%).

I.R. spectrum showed characteristic bands at 1740 cm^{-1} , 1710 cm^{-1} (broad), 1450 cm^{-1} , 1375 cm^{-1} and 1030 cm^{-1} .

2-Methyl-8-ethoxy-4,8-oxy-4-nonane-5-carboxylic acid (VII) : The diketoeester (V, 7 g.) was dissolved in dioxane (65 ml.) and triethyl-orthoformate (7 ml.) containing para toluene sulphonic acid (1.6 g.). After allowing the solution to stand at 20° for 3 hrs, the acid was neutralised with pyridine and water was added. Extraction with ether, drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate and removal of the solvent under pressure yielded the ester (VI, 4 g.) which was used as such for the next step.

A solution of the above ester (VI, 4 g.) in water (7 ml.) and ethyl alcohol (4.5 ml. containing 4.5 g. of KOH) was refluxed for 48 hrs. Thereafter the solution was cooled and the unreacted ester removed by extraction with ether. The aqueous layer was acidified with dilute HCl, extracted with ether and the extract dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent furnished the acid (VII, 2.6 g.) which was not further purified.

2 : 6-Diketo-8-methyl-nonane (III) : The above acid (2.6 g.) was dissolved in dioxane (15 ml.) and water (5 ml. containing 0.45 g. of P.T.S.) and the solution allowed to stand at 20° for 15 hrs. Extraction with ether, washing the extract with NaHCO₃ solution and water, drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporation of the solvent afforded a residue which was distilled under vacuum to furnish the diketone. (III, 1.2 g.), b.p. 102–106°/7–8 mm; η_D^{34} 1.5136. (Found : C, 70.62; H, 10.71. C₁₀H₁₈O₂ requires : C, 70.54; H, 10.66%).

I.R. spectrum of this diketone was exactly superimposable with that of the sample prepared by the sulphoxide route.

2 : 6-Diketo-4 : 4 : 8-trimethyl-nonane (IIIa) : The anion (II) was subjected to the reaction of mesityl oxide exactly according to the conditions described in the synthesis of (III) affording (IIIa) in 50 per cent yield, b.p. 104–106°/7 mm., η_D^{34} 1.5032. (Found : C, 72.92; H, 10.99. C₁₂H₂₂O₂ requires : C, 72.68; H, 11.18%).

I.R. spectrum showed characteristic bands at 1710 cm⁻¹, broad, (ketone), 1450 cm⁻¹ and 1375 cm⁻¹ (C–Me).

3-Methyl-3(4-methyl-pentanone-2)-cyclohexanone (IIIb) : The reaction of 3-methyl-cyclohex-2-ene-1-one (2.2 g.) with anion (II) was also carried out under the usual conditions to furnish the diketone (IIIb), b.p. 145–148°/7 mm. yield 2.18 g. (56 per cent); η_D^{34} 1.5455. (Found : C, 74.43; H, 10.42. C₁₃H₂₂O₂ requires : C, 74.24; H, 10.54%).

I.R. spectrum showed prominent bands at 1710 cm⁻¹, 1455 cm⁻¹ and 1380 cm⁻¹.

1-Carbethoxy-6-methyl-heptan-4-one (VIII) : Ethyl acrylate (2.0 g.) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of the anion (II), prepared in the usual manner of (III) from β -ketosulphoxide (I, 3.0 g.), sodium ethoxide (1.3 g.) and anhydrous D.M.F. (20 ml.) at room temperature. After the usual working the alkylated product (3.9 g.) was cleaved with aluminium amalgam (5.5 g. Al.) in 10 per cent aqueous T.H.F. (240 ml.) to provide the ketoester (VIII), b.p. 115–20°/100 mm., yield 2.4 g. (65%); η_D^{34} 1.4780. (Found : C, 66.12; H, 10.02. C₁₁H₂₀O₃ requires : C, 65.97; H, 10.07%).

I.R. spectrum showed prominent bands at 2950, 1740, 1710, 1465, 1375, 1240, 1170, 1090, 1030, 950, 920 and 855 cm⁻¹.

1-Carbethoxy-1,6-dimethyl-heptan-4-one (VIIIa) : Alkylation of anion (II), prepared from β -ketosulphoxide (I) (3.0 g.), sodium ethoxide (1.3 g.) in D.M.F., with ethyl- α -methylacrylate (2.25 g.) and subsequent cleavage of the methylsulphinyl group with aluminium amalgam (5.0 g.) in T.H.F. (10 per cent aqueous solution) as described above afforded

(VIIIa), b.p. 110°/7 mm., yield 2.10 g. (53 per cent); η_D^{34} 1.4803. (Found : C, 67.42; H, 10.18. $C_{12}H_{22}O_3$ requires : C, 67.25; H, 10.35%)

I.R. spectrum showed prominent bands at 2950, 1740, 1710, 1465, 1375, 1245, 1170, 1090, 1040, 955, 920, and 860 cm^{-1} .

1-Carboethoxy-2,6-dimethyl-heptan-4-one (VIIIb) : The anion (II) was prepared from β -ketosulphoxide (I, 2.0 g.) and sodium ethoxide (0.9 g.) in dry D.M.F. The alkylation was carried out with ethyl crotonate (1.50 g.) as described under (III). The resulting alkylated product was subjected to reductive cleavage with aluminium amalgam (4.0 g.) in T.H.F. under the conditions mentioned above to obtain (VIIIb), b.p. 105–107°/7 mm; 1.63 g. (62 percent); η_D^{34} 1.4858. (Found : C, 67.48; H, 10.21. $C_{12}H_{22}O_3$ requires : C, 67.25; H, 10.35%).

I.R. bands at 2970, 1735, 1715, 1470, 1360, 1240, 1165, 1090, 1040, 960, 925 and 855 cm^{-1} .

1-Cyano-6-methyl-heptan-4-one (IX) : To the anion (II), prepared from β -ketosulphoxide (I), (3.0 g.), sodium ethoxide (1.3 g.) and D.M.F. (20 ml.), was added acrylic nitrile (1.0 g.) dropwise and with stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight and then worked up as described earlier. Reductive cleavage of the resulting product under usual conditions provided the cyano ketone (IX), b.p. 110–115°/10 mm., yield 1.96 g. (70 per cent), η_D^{34} 1.4812. (Found : C, 70.42; H, 9.79; N, 9.06. $C_9H_{15}N$ requires : C, 70.55; H, 9.87; N, 9.14%).

Characteristic I.R. peaks at 2225 cm^{-1} (–CN) and 1705 cm^{-1} (–C = O) confirmed the structure of the synthesised product (IX).

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